

A Study on the Segmentation of School Teachers Job Stress with Special Reference to Cuddalore District

* Dr.V.Sumathy, **DR.G.S.Subashini

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration,

*Thiru Kolanjiyappar Government Arts College, Vrithachalam.

**Kunthavai Naacchiyar Government Arts College, Thanjavur-7.

vsumathysenthil@yahoo.co.in, g.s.subashinithanjavur@gmail.com

Abstract- The worker's response to work stress can be either psychological, physical or both and is usually categorized as being acute, post traumatic, or chronic. National surveys in the United Kingdom, Australia and India have reported a serious and growing problem of academic work stress with several deleterious consequences including decreased job satisfaction, reduced morale and ill health for academic staff. The outcome of stress may be of: emotional manifestations, dissatisfaction, depression, feelings of undefined anxiety, fear and low self-esteem with a possible extreme result being burnout; behavioral manifestations - behavioral issues such as hungry disorders, excessive smoking and alcohol or drug abuse, violence, sleep disorders, possible displays of withdrawal symptoms that is absence and resignations from the profession. Stress is an incidence that must be predictable and addressed in various professions- the teaching profession is no exception.

Key words: Job stress, Depression, Teacher stress, job satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Role stress may be viewed as the consequence of disparity between an individual's perception of the characteristics of a specific role and what is actually being achieved by the individual currently performing the specific role. Thus, role stress occurs when there is difference between perceived role expectations and achievement. Burnout is defined as a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment, and found that burnout is strongly related to work overload, a lack of social support and role stress. The objective of the study is to segment the respondents based on the level of stress and their significant relationship between the clusters. Further, the researcher identifies the association between income, practicing specific activities and level of stress.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Tasleema et al.(2013), The measurement of social and family role stress among primary school teachers. The Social and Family Role Stress Scale (SFRS) by S. Sultan Akhter and Priti Vadra were administered. The analysis of the data showed that Female primary school teachers were found to have more stress as compared to male primary school teachers of District Budgam.

Durban (2013) examined the different sources of stress among elementary school teachers in Metro Manila. The samples were randomly chosen among elementary school teachers. The study reports that of the four sources of stress identified, the Pupils' behaviour and achievement recorded a significant difference among the variables identified. Results indicate that of the different sources of stress students' behaviour was considered as having the most significant influence among teachers.

Martin (2009) defined stress as unpleasant state of emotional and physiological arousal that people experience in situations that they perceive as dangerous or threatening to their well-being. The word stress means different things to different people. Stress is defined as events or situations that cause them to feel tension, pressure, or negative emotions such as anxiety and anger. Others view stress as the response to these situations. This response includes physiological changes—such as increased heart rate and muscle tension—as well as emotional and behavioral changes. However, most psychologists regard stress as a process involving a person's interpretation and response to a threatening event.

III. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study to find the relationship between the variables. Primary and secondary data was composed for the study. To gather the data from the respondents

random sampling technique was used. About 390 public and private are taken for the study. The teachers' age ranged from 25 to >45 years (49 per cent aged between 31 to 35). The majority of teachers were married and the majority of the respondents had been teaching from 1 to 10 years. As per the formula the estimated sample size required for the study is 390, so the researcher choose sample size is 390 as shown in table 1. Questionnaire was taken from Job Stress outcomes - Teacher Stress Inventory (Schutz & Long, 1988) The shortened version has 36 items that are rated on a 5-point Likert scale. These items are grouped into seven categories which include: role ambiguity; role stress ; organizational management ; job satisfaction ; life satisfaction ; task stress and supervisory support .A high score indicates a higher degree of stress experienced by the participant. A high score indicates that the teachers has a high amount of stress in that area. The maximum score is 180. To analyze the collected data researcher used cluster analysis and chi-square test using SPSS software.

TABLE 1: NUMBER OF SCHOOLS TAKEN FOR THE STUDY

Type of school	Available	Percentage in total	Required Sample size
Public	7,942	45.6 %	178
Private Aided	2,811	16.2%	63
Private Unaided	6,640	38.2%	149
Total	17,393	100%	390

TABLE 3: FINAL CLUSTER CENTERS FOR SEGMENTATION OF TEACHERS STRESS

Stress level	Clusters					
	Segment1	Rank	Segment 2	Rank	Segment 3	Rank
Supervisory Support	4.03	I	3.18	II	2.53	III
Role ambiguity	4.41	I	3.50	II	2.37	III
Role Stress	4.01	II	4.39	I	2.99	III
Organizational management	3.95	I	3.91	II	2.57	III
Jobs Satisfaction	4.32	I	3.32	II	3.05	III
Life Satisfaction	4.23	I	3.11	II	2.57	III
Task Stress	4.06	I	2.61	II	2.49	III
Average	4.14		3.43		2.65	

Table:3 shows the Final Cluster Centers and the mean values of all the factors of teachers Job Stress in the three final clusters. The mean values of Teachers Job Stress in the final clusters centers table

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This procedure attempts to identify relatively homogeneous groups of cases based on the selected characteristics, using an algorithm that can handle large numbers of cases. The Teachers Job Stress can be classified into three categories based on Stress level they have on Supervisory Support, Role ambiguity, Role Stress, Organizational management, Jobs Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction and Task Stress. Based on the cluster analysis teachers job stress is classified into three segments because the difference among the coefficients is significant only on three cases on the hierarchical cluster. For the function of categorization of investors K-Means cluster is used.

TABLE 2: NUMBER OF CASES IN EACH CLUSTER

Cluster	1	110.00	28.20%
	2	107.00	27.44%
	3	173.00	44.36%
Valid		390.00	

The Number of cases in each cluster table indicates that around 110 Teachers out of 390 Teachers are in cluster I which is the High level of stress group and 107 out of 390 Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. This means that around 28.20 percent of Teachers are in High level of stress segment and 27.44 percent of Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. In cluster three 44.36 percent of the Teachers are comes under Low level of stress group.

reflect the attributes of each cluster. It is noted from the table that no particular stress factors is heavily loaded on any particular cluster segment. Further, Table 3 portrays that the Teachers Job Stress can be

divided into three distinct clusters based on their response. These clusters was named as “High level of stress”, “Medium level of stress” and “Low level of stress”. The rank of the clusters on Teachers Job Stress is also given in the above table.

TABLE 4 : ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LEVEL OF STRESS AND INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS.

Stress level	Income			Total	Value	Sig. Value
	15001-20000	20001-25000	>25000			
High	9	17	84	110	10.02	0.04
Medium	9	9	89	107		
Low	17	8	148	173		
Total	35	34	321	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Income.

H₁: There is an association between level of stress and Income

The association between the level of stress and the income of respondents has been find out by chi-square tests. From the table there are 35 respondents got 150001-20000 as their monthly salary, out of them 17 respondents got low level of stress and 9 of them having high level of stress. There are 321 respondents got more than 25000 as their salary, out of them 84 having high level of stress, and 148 of them low level of stress. The results inferred that the lower the income of the respondents lead to high level of stress that is more than 50 percent of the respondents in the income group 150001 to 20000 having high level of stress, Chi-square value in this research is 10.02, and the p-value is 0.04 so it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between the level of stress and income of the respondents, so the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The variables

considered in the study, such as age, educational qualification, nature of the subjects the teachers teaching, community, marital status, salary received by the teachers and location of the school are considerably forecast the occupational stress of higher secondary teachers. The studies from Mariya (2012) shows there is no significant difference between monthly salary and occupational stress among school teachers. Teachers with lower monthly income are having higher stress when compared with their colleagues with higher monthly income.

Figure: 1 portrays the results of Correspondence Analysis to explore the association between the income and teachers job stress. The Figure: 1 displays that teachers income falls between 15001 to 20000 are closely associated with “Low level of stress group”, while teachers income greater than 25000 are closely associated “Medium level of stress” group. Teacher’s income between 20001 to 25000 is closely associated with the “High level of stress”.

Figure 1 : Associations between Income and Level of Job Stress

TABLE 5: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LEVEL OF STRESS AND PRACTICING SPECIFIC ACTIVITIES

Stress Level	pPracticing specific activities						Total	Value	Sig. Value
	Yoga	meditation	music	sports	religious activities	nothing			
High	10	17	0	9	20	54	110	219.50	0.00
Medium	9	9	19	9	52	9	107		
Low	17	80	42	17	17	0	173		
Total	36	106	61	35	89	63	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and practicing specific activities

H₁: There is an association between level of stress and practicing specific activities

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the level of stress and specific activity practicing. From the results it is inferred that there are 36 respondents who are practicing yoga out of them 10 are having high level of stress, 17 of them avail with low level of stress, 106 respondents doing meditation out of them 17 are having high level of stress, 80 of them having low level of stress, 61 respondents having interest in music out of them 42 of them having low level of stress and none of them inferred with high level of stress, there are 35 respondents practicing sports activity and out of that 9 of them having high level of stress and 9 of them having medium level of stress and 17 of them having low level of stress. There are 89 respondents coped with religious activity out of them 20 of them having high level of stress, 17 of them having low level of stress, there are 63 respondents not interest in any activities to relieve stress out of that 63, 54 of them having high level of stress, 9 of them having medium level of stress, no one is inferred with low level of stress. The chi-square value for this table is 219.50 with respective 0.00 p-value it is inferred that there is a statistical significant association between the level of stress and practicing specific activities. The study by Anderson (1999) employed a pretest-posttest control group design and used the Teacher's Stress Inventory (TSI), State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), and the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) to assess the effect of a 5-week standardized meditation (SM) class on the perceived occupational stress of 91 full-time teachers from seven suburban school districts in three states. Results were consistent with the hypothesis that SM significantly reduces teachers' perceived stress.

Figure 2 : Associations between practicing specific activities and the level of teachers Job Stress

Figure:2 portrays the results of Correspondence Analysis to explore the association between practicing of specific activities teachers' job stress. The Figure 2 displays that teachers those who are practicing and having interest in music and meditation are closely associated with "Low level of stress group", while teachers following spiritual activities are intimately associated "Medium level of stress" group. Teachers those who are not practicing any activities are closely associated with the "High level of stress"

V. CONCLUSION

The progress of the country depends upon the quality of teachers, building, equipments, instructional material, up-to-date library, well developed curriculum etc. These all are necessary but, without qualified and highly motivated teachers, these are of no value. Teacher is considered as a core stone of successful education system. A number of external and internal factors acts upon a teacher and influences his/her behavior in implementing the education policy of nation. So there is need to identify these factors which influence the teacher. The teacher plays an important role in shaping the behavior of student especially in beginning years. A teacher who is satisfied with his job can perform his duties efficiently and effectively and has a positive attitude towards teaching, but if the teacher is in under stress then the teacher cannot work effectively and has a negative attitude towards his job.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Al-khalefa, S.M. (1999), Female PE teacher stress in primary schools in the Kingdom of Bahrain. Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Physical Education College in AL Harem, Cairo, Egypt.
- [2]. Anderson, V. L., Levinson, E. M., Barker, W., & Kiewra, K. R. (1999). The effects of meditation on teacher perceived occupational stress, state and trait anxiety, and burnout. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 14(1), 3-25.
- [3]. Durban, J. M. & Alontaga, J. V. (2013), A self assessment of the professional stress among elementary school teachers. *European Social Sciences Research Journal*, Vol. 1, Issue 1, January 2013, 19-28.
- [4]. Howard, S. & Johnson, B. (2004), Resilient teachers: Resisting stress and burnout. *Social Psychology of Education*, 7, 399-420.
- [5]. Manjula, (2012), A Study on Personality Factors Causing Stress among School Teachers, *Strength for Today and Bright Hope for Tomorrow*, Volume 12 : 2 February 2012, ISSN 1930-2940.
- [6]. Martin Kwasi Abiemo(2009), Literature Review On Stress Management, HO Polytechnic Department Of Sec. & mgt. Stds. Hnd sec. & mgt. Stds. III, 2009, 1 – 21

- [7]. Mariya Aftab, Tahira Khatoon(2012), Demographic Differences And Occupational Stress Of Secondary School Teachers, European Scientific Journal March edition vol. 8, No.5 ISSN: 1857 – 7881 (Print) e - ISSN 1857- 7431.
- [8]. Schutz, R.W. & Long, B.C. (1988). Confirmatory factor analysis, validation and revision of a teacher stress inventory. Educational and Psychological Measurement, 48, 497-511.
- [9]. Tasleema Jan et al. (2013), A Study Of Social And Family Role Stress Among Primary School Teachers of District Budgam, J&K, India, Journal Of Educational Research And Essays, Vol. 1(1), Pp. 1- 4 Jan. 2013 .
- [10]. Tytherleigh, M. Y., Webb, C., Cooper, C. L., and Ricketts, C., (2005), “Occupational Stress in UK Higher Education Institutions: A Comparative Study of All Staff Categories”, Higher Education Research and Development, 24 (1), February, pp. 41-61.
- [11]. Winefield, A. H., and Jarrett, H.,(2001), “Occupational stress in university staff”. International Journal of Stress Management, 8 (4), October, pp. 285-298.